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Implementation of Tourism Development Policies in Garut District, West Java Province, Indonesia

Achmad Rizal

Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science, Universitas Padjadjaran,
Jl. Raya Jatinangor Km 21, Jatinangor, Sumedang 45363, West Java, Indonesia

E-mail address: achmad.rizal@unpad.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

The Government of Garut District launched the priority of 10 tourist destinations' development program to be more comfortable and secure based on the visits rate assessment results and a promising tourism potential to many visitors. This report aims to determine the implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District, which were reviewed with the criteria approach, namely attraction, accessibility, and amenities. This reporting approaches describe the implementation of tourism development policies in the Garut District. The results show the implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District has been going well even though several problems still exist. Some of the problems identified include accessibility that is still not very supportive, such as the road to the location of tourism being relatively small. Facilities and infrastructure in tourism objects have not been appropriately managed due to budget constraints, as well as the low awareness of the public about the culture of tourism awareness and the tourism benefits.

Keywords: Garut District, Policy Implementation, Tourism, Development Policy, West Java Province, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Garut District is one of the tourist destinations in West Java. Tourism development is realized through the implementation of a tourism development plan by taking into account the diversity, and uniqueness of culture and nature and human needs for tourism. District Tourism Strategic Areas, from now on abbreviated as DTSA, are areas that have the primary function of tourism or have the potential for tourism development which has an important influence in one or more aspects, such as economic, social, and cultural growth, empowerment of natural resources, environmental carrying capacity, and defense and security.

Following the Garut District Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2019 concerning the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan, that the vision of regional tourism development in the District is the realization of the District as a leading nature-based tourism destination in West Java supported by a culture that is competitive and sustainable, to be devout, advanced, and prosperous.

Tourism relies heavily on the uniqueness, localization, and authenticity of nature and culture that grows in society. Looking at the meaning in the Garut District Regional Regulation of West Java Province Number 2 of 2019 concerning the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan, tourism is a variety of tourist activities. It is supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, business people, government, and local governments. Meanwhile, tourism is a travel activity carried out by a person or group of people by visiting certain places for recreational purposes, personal development, or learning the uniqueness of the tourist attraction visited for a temporary period.

Meanwhile, the tourist attraction is anything that has uniqueness, beauty, and value in the form of a diversity of natural, cultural, and human-made wealth that is the target or purpose of tourist visits. The number of visits from outside the city to Garut District is an important factor to observe regarding tourist areas. With the various tourist objects, the local government of

Garut District needs to prepare itself as a tourist destination that has competitiveness. One of these is by creating reliable tourism products to play a role as a contributor to foreign exchange for national tourism and spurring regional tourism businesses to become an essential element to increase the community's economy and Regional Original Income (ROI).

Besides, as a tourist destination, Garut District must be able to provide adequate services for tourists. Souvenir sales centers are needed to make it easier for tourists to get the souvenirs they want—likewise, culinary centers. The facilities do not need to be luxurious but must be neat and clean to attract tourists. With the potential that exists in Garut District, it is appropriate that the Garut District Government seeks to improve the welfare of the community from the tourism and trade sectors and agriculture, plantations and livestock, and existing small industries. These sectors will support each other and open up opportunities to create new jobs for the community.

It is necessary to compare the parties directly involved in these problems to improve society's welfare and optimize the potential for tourism and trade in Garut District; the institutions that play a direct role are the Department of Tourism and Culture and the Department of Industry, Trade, Energy and Mineral Resources, the Office of Cooperatives and SMEs, and the Office of Manpower Transmigration of Garut District.

Apart from policy, several other determining factors are the availability of supporting facilities that can contribute to the development of tourist objects in the Garut District. Some of the facilities that must be available are accommodation and transportation and other support related to tourist objects or trade places such as terminals, parking facilities, shelters, playgrounds, souvenir centers, and public toilets. Of course, this must go hand in hand with the development of infrastructure for existing tourist objects and trade locations to complement each other.

The policy for developing tourism and trade potential in Garut District will undoubtedly be influenced by factors both internally and externally. The Garut District government must make various efforts to make the best use of the existing factors. In this effort, local government programs or policies are needed that facilitate and provide convenience to the community. It is hoped that the community can manage all the potential that exists optimally. Internal factors have a very dominant role as a form of self-organizing in society. The community is asked to indirectly have an awareness of the potential that can positively impact overall economic development.

Efforts to increase tourism potential have been carried out by related parties, in this case, the Tourism and Culture Office, by providing easy licensing. This effort opens up more opportunities for investors to invest in potential tourism sectors in Garut District. The ease of licensing had a positive impact on the development of trade in the Garut District. The addition of tourism locations and the opportunity to open a business urgently take enhanced place. The private sector has been working on existing developments, including infrastructure development, accommodation facilities, and large-scale promotions. The management, which is almost entirely carried out by the private sector, makes the Regional Original Income (ROI) following the Regional Budget Plan (RBP) of Garut District is not too large; it only relies on taxes. The community's expectations, among others, are to increase the ROI and RBP of Garut District. It is necessary to increase the income tax on tourism assets and regional trade.

Several similar reports include [1-11] with the conclusion of their report that there are 16 tourism stakeholders in Biak Numfor District, and most of them serve as subjects, name holders who have high interest but low influence. The needs are expected by tourism stakeholders in

Biak Numfor District for the District, namely: (1) understanding of tourism destinations; (2) coordination between tourism stakeholders; (3) synergy of tourism development programs in Biak Numfor District; and (4) ongoing assistance.

Another report by [1-11] concluded that the ideal tourism policy model is community-based tourism. Some of the obstacles that can be identified are a lack of synergy/communication between stakeholders, a lack of competency in implementing policies, and a lack of community participation. On the other hand, high commitment from local political leaders and good support of resource facilities are the supporting factors for policy. Furthermore, [10-25] report concludes that policy implementation has been implemented, but there are obstacles including lack of communication among stakeholders; competence in implementing policies is still low, and community participation is still lacking.

These studies have something in common with researchers doing, namely the research locus at the district government level, and the analysis is based on the dimensions of policy theory, implementation theory with dimensions of coordination, resources, disposition, and organizational structure [23-60]. Meanwhile, the researcher examined policy implementation with the 3A approach, namely Attraction, Accessibility, and Amenities, to determine the extent of the implementation of tourism development policies. The condition of tourism development in Garut District is not as expected; this is still visible from several problems, including Attraction (natural attractions, cultural arts, customs), which are not managed professionally so that they seem modest. Accessibility in the form of roads to tourist sites/objects narrow so that it often causes congestion, Amenities (facilities) in the form of facilities and infrastructure at tourism objects which have not been appropriately managed so that the appearance conditions are not attractive, and the limited budget owned by the Garut District Government to build and develop tourism potential in Garut District. The culture of tourism awareness is still deficient because people are not aware of the benefits of tourism.

Based on the background description, this report's objectives are: (1) to describe the implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District, and (2) to describe the results of the implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District.

IMPLEMENTATION OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT POLICY IN GARUT DISTRICT

Garut District is one of the areas in West Java Province, covering an area of 306.688 hectares or 6.94% of West Java Province. Geographical location is in the south of West Java Province with coordinates 6°57'34" - 7°44'57" South Latitude and 107°24'3" - 108°24'34" East Longitude, with regional boundaries of Northside, bordering Bandung and Sumedang Regencies. In the south, bordering the Indonesian Ocean, Westside bordering Bandung District and Cianjur District, and in the east, bordering Tasikmalaya District (**Photos 1 and 2**).

Administratively, the government area of Garut District consists of 42 Districts, 94 Villages. (Department of Tourism and Culture of Garut District, 2018). Garut District is rich in potential natural and cultural attractions, known as MONAFESBRIC (Mountains, Natural Forest, Sea, Beach, River, and Cultural Arts), to be developed into a tourist attraction. The tourist attraction in Garut District has progressed along with the efforts that have been made by tourism actors in Garut District. The division of tourist attractions in Garut District is divided into natural tourist attractions, cultural tourist attractions, and artificial ones.

Tourist attractions, both natural, cultural, and artificial tourism in Garut District, are described according to the Strategic Tourism area of Garut District (DTSA). Based on the four DTSA, the Garut District Government has launched a priority program to develop ten tourist destinations to make them more comfortable and safer. This development was carried out to boost domestic and foreign tourist visits in Garut. The priority program for ten tourist destinations is *Bagendit* tourism object in *Banyuresmi* Sub-district, *Situ Canguang* in *Leles* Sub-district, *Sayangheulang* Beach in *Pameungpeuk* District, *Cijeruk*, *Karang Paranje* in *Cibalong* Sub-district, *Rancabuaya* Beach in *Caringin* Sub-district, *Talaga Bodas* crater in *Pangatikan* Sub-district, *Kamojang* area tours in *Samarang* Sub-district, *Cikembulan* Zoo in *Kadungora* Sub-district, and *Darajat* hot springs in *Pasirwangi* Sub-district. Determination of priority tourist destinations is based on assessing the level of visits and good tourism potential such as many visitors. The development program or development of tourist destinations in Garut is strived to run as expected so that it has a good impact on Garut tourism, significantly growing the economy of the Garut community (**Photos 3 to 8**).

The tourism development policy in Garut District is always directed at three aspects that are expected to reach all development sectors, namely increasing economic growth, expanding business opportunities, and keeping development running sustainably. This is based on the concept of regional development, which improves the community's economy and improves the social, economic, political order, and sustainable welfare of the people.

The tourism potential of Garut District has factually become one of the sources of ROI and supports the economic development of the community so that it has development prospects in the future. With the programs that have been implemented as a manifestation of the implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District by the Department of Tourism and Culture, implementing the program is shown in the following tables.

Based on **Table 1**, in general, the number of tourists visiting Garut District from year to year fluctuates in the number of visits related to information on travel trips to Garut District and its surroundings, which is not optimal so that it sometimes confuses potential tourists. Especially for those who come to Garut District for the first time and don't know anything about Garut District, they will find it difficult to determine their next tourist destination.

Table 1. Development of Tourist Attractions and Accommodation Visits

Year	Accommodation		Tourism site	
	International Tourists	Domestic Tourists	International Tourists	Domestic Tourists
2015	1.941	182.196	5.261	776.796
2016	3.993	234.688	7.189	879.862
2017	2.648	235.136	8.280	797.316
2018	3.555	214.743	4.055	929.569

Source: Department of Tourism and Culture of Garut District, 2020.

Table 2. Most Visits of Nature Tourism Objects in 2019

Nature Tourism Objects	Number of visitors
Cipanas	227.631
Situ Bagendit	75.963
Santolo Beach	45.008
Rancabuaya Beach	41.178
Sayangheulang Beach	36.668
Lapang Golf Ngamplang	30.393
Curug Orok	27.268

Source: Department of Tourism and Culture of Garut District, 2020.

In **Table 2**, the natural tourism object that has the highest level of visits is *Cipanas*, where the high level of visits is due to several factors, among others: *Cipanas* is one of the main and favorite tourist destinations in Garut District (**Photos 9 to 49**), a natural tourist destination to enjoy hot water that comes from an active volcano, namely Mount Guntur, which is well known outside the city. *Cipanas* tourist attraction is very strategic because it is close to the city center and accommodation facilities. *Cangkuang* Cultural Heritage is a tourist area located in the middle of a small lake (Situ) consisting of *Cangkuang* Temple, the traditional settlement of *Kampung Pulo*, and the grave of *Embah Dalem Arief Muhammad*, who is the ancestor of *Kampung Pulo*. Access to tourist sites is quite good even though the road width is relatively small so that large vehicles such as buses cannot enter, so they have to use public transportation (**Photos 50 and 51**).

Table 3. Most Visits of Cultural Tourism Objects in 2019

Cultural Tourism Objects	Number of visitors
<i>Cangkuang</i> Cultural Heritage	46.327
<i>Kampung Dukuh</i>	20.244
<i>Ciburuy</i> Cultural Heritage	15.055

Source: Department of Tourism and Culture of Garut District, 2020.

The results of the implementation of development programs in the field of tourism when analyzed and assessed are based on the criteria proposed by [50-60], namely attraction,

accessibility, and amenities (facilities), then behind the successful implementation of tourism development policies in Garut District through programs which are carried out by the Garut District Tourism and Culture Office. On the other hand, there are still unresolved problems, among others, third parties, namely investors as capital owners, often do not consult in developing tourism businesses to Regional Planning Agency so that they are not following Regional Tourism Master Plan (RTMP) and Spatial plans. For example, many investors who have built new tourist objects report to the Integrated Investment and Licensing Agency. These developments sometimes do not comply with the RTMP and spatial plans, so they are considered problematic.

The Special Allocation Fund of 5 billion in 2020 is only focused on developing tourism objects *Situ Bagendit, Cangkuang, and Sayang Heulang*, so that other tourist objects do not receive development funds. The accessibility is still not supportive of tourist locations where the roads are still narrow, causing congestion and impacting the number of tourist visits. Facilities and infrastructure in tourist objects have not been appropriately managed because of the Garut District Government's limited budget. This has an impact on the comfort of tourists when visiting tourist objects.

The tourism awareness culture program is still deficient, and this is because people are not aware of the benefits of tourism and lack of socialization and information about tourism objects in Garut District.

CONCLUSION

The Garut District Tourism and Culture Office's implementation of tourism development policies has gone well. However, tourism development in Garut District is not optimal where there are still unresolved problems that impact the interest of tourist visits to tourist objects in Garut District. In connection with the ease of accessibility for investors in obtaining permits for the development of infrastructure or tourism facilities, it is necessary to increase coordination and consultation among stakeholders so that there is a common understanding in implementing tourism development policies in Garut District.

Planning priorities for the budget allocation for the development of tourism facilities and infrastructure are based on the DTSA of Garut District and involving companies' CSR programs in Garut District. Increasing the socialization of tourism awareness culture involves non-governmental organizations and communities that care about tourism and form tourism cadres who care about tourism development in Garut District.

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APPENDIX

GARUT DISTRICT IN INDOONESIAN MAP

Photo 1

Photo 3.

Photo 4.

Photo 5

Photo 6

Photo 7

Photo 8

Photo 9

Photo 10

Photo 11

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Photo 27

Photo 28

Photo 29

Photo 30

Photo 31

Photo 32

Photo 33

Photo 34

Photo 35

Photo 36

Photo 37

Photo 38

Photo 39

Photo 40

Photo 41

Photo 42

Photo 43

Photo 44

Photo 45

Photo 46

Photo 47

Photo 48

Photo 49

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Photo 51